

ESTIMATION OF SEVERITY OF SPEECH DISABILITY THROUGH SPEECH ENVELOPE

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, envelope detection of speech is discussed to distinguish the pathological cases of speech disabled children. The speech signal samples of children of age between five to eight years are considered for the present study. These speech signals are digitized and are used to determine the speech envelope. The envelope is subjected to ratio mean analysis to estimate the disability. This analysis is conducted on ten speech signal samples which are related to both place of articulation and manner of articulation. Overall speech disability of a pathological subject is estimated based on the results of above analysis.

KEYWORDS

Envelope, Mean Analysis, Pathology, Ratio and Speech

1. INTRODUCTION

Speech is one of the very important medium of communication. The quality of speech must be such that the information content must be easily be understood by human listeners. Speech disability is one of the widely encountered disabilities in children. In this direction, many researchers have tried different methods to analyze the speech using different envelope techniques like autocorrelation envelope, temporal envelope, power envelope and spectral envelope. A new speech measure based on parameterization of the autocorrelation envelope of the AM response is developed for vocal fold pathology assessment [11]. Voice conversion system is created to change the perceived speaker identity of a speech signal, which is based on converting the LPC spectrum and predicting the residual as a function of the target envelope parameters [1]. An algorithm is developed to detect speech pauses by adaptively tracking minima in a noisy signal's power envelope both for the broadband signal and for the high-pass and low-pass filtered signal [17]. A method based on the temporal envelope representation of speech is developed to reflect the perceptual characteristics of human auditory system and human speech production system [8]. The estimate of the spectral envelope by linear prediction has sharp peaks for high-pitch speakers. To overcome this, regularized linear prediction is applied to find a better estimate of the spectral envelope [14]. All pole spectral envelope

estimation for speech signals is addressed by establishing a band limited interpolation of the observed spectrum by using a recently rediscovered true envelope estimator and then using the band limited envelope to derive an all pole envelope model. [9]. It is confirmed that a speaker's vocal individuality is contained in the inter-band correlations of narrow-band temporal envelopes. Two types of envelope correlation matrices (ECMs) were made, using three utterances of an identical sentence. Type-A (reference) ECMs of two of the utterances were constructed to make a speaker's individual template and a type-B ECM was constructed using the other utterance. Speaker matching tests between the two types of ECMs were conducted to verify the validity of the individual speakers [19]. In this paper, an attempt is made to distinguish the cases of pathological subjects with respect to normal subject by using speech envelope technique. In this present work, the speech uttered by children of age group of 5 to 8 years was recorded and digitized. The digitized signal was further processed by using a high level computational platform MATLAB.

2. METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted on children of native speakers of Kannada language. Prior to the data collection, teachers were requested to train the normal children aged between 5 and 8 years, to read a few words/sentences. The sentences read by children were recorded using Intelligent Portable Occular Device (IPOD) in digital form. The recording was carried out in a pleasant atmosphere. The recorded signal is transformed into .wav file by using GOLDWAVE software. The same procedure is also followed while recording the speech samples of children with speech disorder. The data was collected at J.S.S. 'Sahana' integrated and special school located at Bangalore, India.

Energy level for a particular recorded word "Namma" pronounced by 60 normal children was found and average energy level is calculated. The energy level of the child which is very close to average energy level is considered as Normal Subject. The child with speech disability is considered as a Pathological Subject.

The speech disorder [1, 8] depends on the problems associated with either place of articulation [15] or manner of articulation or both. The specific letters shown in the Table-1 may not be enough to study the speech disorder completely. Words with more than two letters result in greater computational complexity in computing speech disorder. Hence, in the present study, emphasis is given for words with two letters particularly ending with a specific letter shown in the Table-1.

Table-1. List of specific Kannada letters/ words

SI No.	Place of articulation	Manner of articulation	Kannada Letters	words in Kannada language
1	Bilabial	Nasals	ಮ (m)	ನಮ್ಮ (Namma)
2	Dental	Nasals	ನ (n)	ನನ್ನ (Nanna)
3	Dental	Fricatives	ತ (t), ದ (d)	ಇದ (Ide)
4	Alveolar	Laterals	ಲ (l), ಳ (L)	ಶಾಲೆ (Shale)
5	Bilabial	Stops	ಪ (p), ಬ (b)	ಜೆಪಿ (Jepi)

6	Palatal	Affricates	ಜ'(j), ಸ(s) ಶ(sha)	ಹೆಸ (Hesa)
7	Velar	Plosives	ಕ(k), ಗ(g)	ನಗ (Naga)
8	Glottal		ಹ(h)	ಸಹ (Saha)
9		Trills	ರ(r)	ದೊರ (Doora)
10		Glides	ಯ(y)	ಜಯ (Jaya)

3. DETERMINATION OF ENVELOPE OF SPEECH SIGNAL

The Recorded speech signals samples for common Kannada word “Namma” uttered by normal subject is considered. Start and end points of this word is determined. The digitized speech signal consists of total 21121 samples. The sample count is rounded down to nearest hundred by removing the trailing samples. The speech signal is divided into multiple blocks with block size of 100 samples [5]. In each block, maximum and minimum values of the samples are determined. The speech envelope of this block is determined by linearly interpolation [5] of samples in between maximum and minimum values. The same procedure is applied for all the blocks to determine the complete envelope of the uttered word “Namma”. The speech signal and the corresponding envelope is indicated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Amplitude plot and Envelope of the word “Namma” of Normal Subject

4. DETERMINATION OF THRESHOLD

To calculate the threshold value, three utterances of the word “Namma” by Normal Subject were considered. Envelope of each of these samples is calculated. Envelope of first utterance is treated as the reference. Ratio of absolute value of envelope of second utterance and first utterance and that of third and first utterance is calculated. Mean values of the ratios are calculated. Out of these two values, minimum value is chosen as threshold value.

5. ESTIMATION OF SPEECH DISABILITY

Speech signal samples of the uttered word “Namma” by three pathological subjects are considered. The length of samples is equated to that of normal subject. Envelopes of these utterances are determined. For each pathological subject, mean of absolute ratio between envelope of pathological subject and envelope of normal subject is calculated. This analysis

method is repeated for all the words indicated in Table-1. The speech signal samples of the word “Namma” uttered by each of three pathological subjects and their corresponding envelopes are shown in Figure 2, Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Figure 2. Amplitude plot and Envelope of the word “Namma” of Pathological Subject 1

Figure 3. Amplitude plot and Envelope of the word “Namma” of Pathological Subject 2

Figure 4. Amplitude plot and Envelope of the word “Namma” of Pathological Subject 3

The limits used for the classification of mild, moderate and severe cases of speech disorders of Pathological Subjects are indicated in Table-2. For this classification, threshold value of 1.03989 is used. This value is obtained from envelope analysis of Normal Subject.

Table-2 Limits for assessment of varying degree of speech disability

No Deviation	Small Deviation	Moderate Deviation	Large Deviation
$0.8 < R_{th} \leq 1.2$	$1.2 < R_{th} \leq 1.8$ or $0.6 \leq R_{th} < 0.8$	$1.8 < R_{th} \leq 2.6$ or $0.4 \leq R_{th} < 0.6$	$R_{th} > 2.6$ or $R_{th} < 0.4$

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Table-3 indicates the result of analysis of three pathological subjects for ten words. The entire analysis is conducted by using MATLAB tool. The summary of the above analysis is represented in Table-4.

Table-3. Result of analysis of various words for the three Pathological Subjects

Pronounced Word	Particulars	Ratio Value	Deviation from the Threshold Value
Namma	Normal and Pathological Subject 1	1.62684	mild
	Normal and Pathological Subject 2	2.60459	moderate
	Normal and Pathological Subject 3	4.22875	severe
Ide	Normal and Pathological Subject 1	0.94963	no
	Normal and Pathological Subject 2	0.45808	moderate
	Normal and Pathological Subject 3	1.35224	mild
Shale	Normal and Pathological Subject 1	1.54192	mild
	Normal and Pathological Subject 2	1.70836	mild
	Normal and Pathological Subject 3	2.19511	moderate
Jepi	Normal and Pathological Subject 1	2.30208	moderate
	Normal and Pathological Subject 2	3.52232	large
	Normal and Pathological Subject 3	3.19259	severe
Hesa	Normal and Pathological Subject 1	1.39495	mild
	Normal and Pathological Subject 2	1.66019	mild
	Normal and Pathological Subject 3	3.23197	severe
Naga	Normal and Pathological Subject 1	1.04994	no
	Normal and Pathological Subject 2	2.05953	moderate
	Normal and Pathological Subject 3	1.09738	no
Saha	Normal and Pathological Subject 1	1.67477	mild
	Normal and Pathological Subject 2	1.43331	mild
	Normal and Pathological Subject 3	2.22832	moderate
Doora	Normal and Pathological Subject 1	0.76715	mild
	Normal and Pathological Subject 2	1.47577	mild
	Normal and Pathological Subject 3	1.42325	mild

Jaya	Normal and Pathological Subject 1	1.20300	no
	Normal and Pathological Subject 2	3.35342	large
	Normal and Pathological Subject 3	2.77495	severe
Nanna	Normal and Pathological Subject 1	1.51143	mild
	Normal and Pathological Subject 2	2.34976	moderate
	Normal and Pathological Subject 3	2.96658	severe

Table-4. Summary of Results

Name of the Subject	No Deviation	Mild Deviation	Moderate Deviation	Large Deviation
Pathological Subject 1	3	6	1	Nil
Pathological Subject 2	Nil	4	4	2
Pathological Subject 3	1	2	2	5

From the Table-4, it can be concluded that the overall severity of speech disability is mild for Pathological Subject 1, moderate with Subject 2 and severe with Subject 3.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The present study presents a method to estimate the severity of speech disability of a speech disabled child by using the speech signal samples. With this, it is possible to detect speech disorder in children at early stages. Hence necessary corrective measures can be taken. The analysis made in the present study helps the speech therapist for finding the degree of improvement in the speech disabled child by analyzing periodically recorded speech samples.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the management of Sri Bhagawan Mahaveer Jain College of Engineering, Bangalore, Nitte Meenakshi Institute of Technology, Bangalore, and J.S.S. 'Sahana' Integrated and special school, Bangalore for their Constant support and encouragement in undertaking the research work.

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